

The Role and Importance of Personnel Motivation in Food Industry Enterprises

Dilafroz Kurbonova Anvarjon qizi

Management Development Institute of Singapore in Tashkent, Senior Lecturer

ABSTRACT: This article discusses the importance and relevance of staff motivation in the food industry, as well as the types of motivation provided by the author and the tools they use in practice. As a result of the study, it was recommended to use non-traditional methods of staff motivation in our country.

KEYWORDS: Motivation, personnel, food industry enterprises, employee incentive mechanism, motivation system, work experience, needs.

INTRODUCTION

Although modern technologies and robots are widely used in manufacturing enterprises in the period of transformation of industries and sectors of the economy, skilled personnel and their aspirations is up to date. Also, one of the most popular ways to improve product quality in manufacturing enterprises is to constantly train staff, increase their creative initiatives and, of course, motivate them.

The management of the enterprise is focused on increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization of production through the involvement of workers in the production process and their financial support, including the improvement of the quality management system.

It should also be noted that large food production companies use different forms of motivation, depending on the mentality, legal and economic basis of the country where the company is located. For example, in Japan, lifelong employment, the use of bonuses related to length of service, the presence of overtime communication with lower-level employees are the main motivating factors [1], in Germany, 10% of the company's time is spent on employees. the addition of a 3 per cent increase to the salary in the following year and the allocation of a service vehicle, the availability of a 13th salary, etc. [2].

In general, staff motivation in food industry enterprises is no different from other manufacturing enterprises. In both cases, motivation is focused on improving and improving product quality.

Today, there are more than 12,000 enterprises specializing in the food industry in the country [3]. It is known that in the territory of our country, mainly small and medium-sized businesses are engaged in food production. For this reason, various means of staff motivation are almost not used in these enterprises. The main reasons for this are:

Research on the wishes and needs of employees is not part of an enterprise strategy;

Additional employee incentives are not included in the financial plan of the enterprise;

The fact that most small and medium-sized businesses do not have additional financial resources to motivate staff;

The fact that most small and medium-sized businesses have employees with secondary and tertiary education and do not have special training and higher education in the food industry does not create a need to encourage them.

The above can be continued again. However, the purpose of this research is to propose the introduction in our country of modern methods of staff motivation in the food industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

When we study the theoretical foundations of motivation, first of all, A. Maslow's "Pyramid of Needs" [4] appears as the main source. This theory proves that motivation is based on growing and evolving needs.

L. According to Yakok-ka, "Business transactions can ultimately be expressed in three words: people, products, profits. People come first. If you don't have a reliable team, nothing else will be done." [5]

The Role and Importance of Personnel Motivation in Food Industry Enterprises

T. Peter, R. Waterman urges business leaders to respect the dignity of their subordinates, to see them as the main source of productivity [6].

A. Morito says that the main source of motivating educated, knowledgeable and skilled employees to work is to stimulate creativity [7].

Among the scientists of the CIS countries Lovcheva M. In [8] 's research, motivation is cited as the primary function of management as well as the primary means of labor orientation.

Nuriddinova A., one of the Uzbek scientists, studied the motivation of labor in industrial enterprises, which is based on the role of motivation in industrial enterprises [9].

Unfortunately, the role of motivation in the food industry has not been studied by Uzbek scientists. In this regard, the study of this topic is relevant.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The process of staff motivation is always one of the most complex functions in front of the enterprise. The study of the relevance and importance of this topic has also been extensive for the author. During the research, methods of scientific research such as scientific abstraction, theoretical research, analysis and synthesis, study of foreign experience were effectively used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Employee motivation is one of the most challenging issues; it was considered even before the understanding of management as a science and has not lost its relevance today as human needs are constantly changing. At the same time, people are the most valuable resource because they can constantly improve. Finding an effective way to manage people is the key to success for food industry businesses. Often employees can be encouraged to work actively with effective moral motivation. In this case, recognizing the value of an individual employee is more effective than a material reward, because, according to psychologists, the effect of increasing income has a positive effect only for three months. The person then continues to move in a familiar mode.

In shaping the motivation system, it is necessary to develop a clear and well-functioning mechanism of its impact on employees. In order to pursue an effective motivational policy in the organization, it is necessary to form a motivational mechanism that takes into account various factors.

Employee incentive mechanism is a set of measures that reflect the impact of the entity on the object of management. Motives are a complex that forms a complex mechanism of motivation that includes needs, claims, incentives, and evaluation of relationships. The mechanism of motivating employees differs depending on the policy of the country and the mentality of the nation, the direction of production of the enterprise.

In Japan, for example, employee incentives are based on the following principles: the more work experience, the higher the position and salary. This means that career growth is directly related to the length of service in the company. The professional ability, qualifications, personal qualities of the employee are important. It also "cancels" the work experience in the workplace where the employee worked before moving to a new job, and only "their" employees will be able to hold a management position [10].

American companies are creating non-standard systems of employee incentives. For example, IBM and AT&T have chosen the path of "family motivation". The average age of most of the company's employees is less than forty, and most of them are married and have children. The administration therefore allows flexible work schedules, helps select nurses and home helpers, and organizes corporate kindergartens and family vacations.

As we have seen in the above experiments, motivation is a concept directly related to human needs. Need leads to waiting, and waiting leads to installation. That is, the staff expects something from the company based on their needs. As a result of his waiting, he prepares for the stimulus and, after accepting the positive setting, begins to act (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Needs and motivation *

The Role and Importance of Personnel Motivation in Food Industry Enterprises

** image author's design*

In modern conditions, a well-built motivation system is an important element of the personnel management system, especially for fast-growing companies, this function of management is relevant.

Economic, administrative, socio-psychological methods of motivation are widely used in practice (Table 1).

Economic methods of motivation include remuneration of labor, disability benefits, employee insurance, overtime pay, compensation for vacancies, payment equal to the income received, financial incentives for employees.

Scanlon and Rucker's employee benefit system is widely used in manufacturing enterprises.

The system of scanning is that the share of wages under the plan is taken into account in the cost of production, and if the share of wages is actually less, then the amount of savings is distributed among them. For example, the company is 25% and the employees are 75%. Part of the amount intended for employees is sent to the reserve fund, the remaining funds are distributed among the team depending on their contribution to the production process.

Rucker's system is that workers receive a bonus of one dollar wage for "pure" production growth.

Table 1. Methods and Types of motivation *

Direct incentives imply a certain exchange of values, ie a person receives an appropriate reward for the work done.	Negative incentives include punishment for failure to do so.	As a result, employees will have the opportunity to develop psychologically, acquire new knowledge and skills.
Types of motivation		
Internal. Internal motives are created by the work itself - it is a sense of achievement, the content and importance of the work done, self-esteem. The easiest way to provide internal motivation is to create appropriate working conditions and formulate the problem correctly.	External. External motives are created by the organization. External motivation (or motivation) can take two forms: 1. Administrative motivation is the performance of work under direct coercion with appropriate sanctions for violation of established norms. 2. Economic incentives - through economic incentives.	
Methods of motivation		
Economic	Administrative	Socio-psychological

** table author's development*

In the Netherlands, the motivational model of benefits and compensations is used in the food industry. If an employee has to visit a doctor or go to the bank, the employer will give them a few hours of work time to solve personal problems - and they will pay in full for that time. And if an employee stays on sick leave for more than three months, he or she is entitled to compensation in the form of additional days of paid leave [11].

Administrative methods of motivating employees in food enterprises include team building and motivation through cooperatives, setting goals and objectives, monitoring their implementation, offering leadership, socio-psychological methods to improve mood and mood, skills development, intelligence, knowledge, self-employment. - Development of various complexes of self-improvement programs.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The role and importance of staff motivation in the food industry during the transformation of production is reflected in the following:

1. On the one hand, a clear understanding of the wishes, needs and requirements of employees will motivate them to follow the requirements of management on product quality and the production of quality products;
2. Indirect economic and non-economic components of the motivation system help to reduce staff turnover and attract highly qualified professionals interested in quality work;
3. Builds employee loyalty to the enterprise, as well as helps to monitor emerging needs of employees and changes in the quality of the final product of the enterprise;
4. Employee motivation is a very important aspect for any manager. If he is interested in ensuring that employees work with the greatest effort and efficiency, he will have to worry about how to arouse the interest of the steps.

The Role and Importance of Personnel Motivation in Food Industry Enterprises

5. The higher the interest of employees in working in the organization and its successful economic activity, the greater the number of benefits and services provided, including services that are not directly defined by applicable law. Such a policy could bring additional income to workers if wages are low.

Based on the above, the author suggests the following:

In our country, it is necessary to use non-traditional methods of staff motivation, including benefits and compensation, employee participation in profits. The use of such methods serves as a motivation for the staff to work on themselves and improve;

According to the author, salary is not motivation. Typically, an employee sees a salary as a payment for the work he or she has done, and expects certain motivations from the company to perform an additional task, to create innovation in the workplace. For this reason, the employee is encouraged to pay bonuses to the staff in the form of separate cash, not added to the salary;

As mentioned above, the food enterprises operating in the country are small or medium-sized businesses, most of which do not define the socio-psychological motivation of staff as the main task of the activity. But the future success of these enterprises and the fact that employees work in the same enterprise for a long time also depends on the socio-psychological factors of motivation.

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